

Synthesis of Some Basic *N*-Thiadiazolyl Acetamides

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Basic acetamides, in which amido-H has been substituted with aromatic or heterocyclic moieties, have been synthesised in large number as potential local anaesthetics. Of these Lidocaine¹ (I) is the most outstanding and satisfactory local anaesthetic². Recently heterocyclic acetamides of type (II)³ have been patented as analgesics and antiapae-modics. It was therefore thought of interest to synthesise the title compounds with a view to studying their biological properties.

[R, R' = H or alkyl]

or $\begin{array}{c} \diagup \text{R} \\ \text{N} \\ \diagdown \text{R}' \end{array}$ = a heterocyclic residue]

The diethylamino-, ethylphenylamino-, diphenylamino-, and piperidinyl-*N* (substituted thiadiazolyl)-acetamides have been prepared by condensing appropriate secondary amines with various 2-chloroacetamido-5-aryl-1,3,4-thiadiazoles in anhydrous ethanol. The latter compounds were obtained by treating a benzene solution of different 2-amino-5-aryl-1,3,4-thiadiazoles with a solution of chloroacetyl chloride in benzene⁴.

Benzoyl thiosemicarbazide, *o*-chloro-, *m*-nitro-, *p*-nitro-, and *p*-hydroxy-benzoyl-thiosemicarbazides were prepared according to the method of Lora-Tamayo *et al*⁵. 2-Amino-5-aryl-1,3,4-thiadiazoles were obtained by cyclisation of appropriate aroyl-thiosemicarbazides⁶.

2-Chloroacetamido-5-phenyl-1,3,4-thiadiazole was prepared according to the method of Bhargava and Singh⁴. A solution of chloroacetyl chloride (11 g.) in benzene (35 ml) was treated with a benzene solution of 2-amino-5-phenyl-1,3,4-thiadiazole (17.7g.) and the reaction mixture was gently refluxed for 1½ hr. The benzene was removed, the residue washed successively with sodium bicarbonate solution and water, and finally

1. Lofgren and Lundquist, U.S.P. 2,441, 498/1948; *Chem. Abs.*, 1948, 42, 6376.

2. Burger, "Medicinal Chemistry", Interscience Publishers, Inc., New York, 2nd ed., p. 465.

3. F. P. 1,281, 280/1961; *Chem. Abs.*, 1962, 58, 10110.

4. *This Journal*, 1961, 38, 77.

5. *Chem. Abs.*, 1958, 53, 2211; Giri and Singh, *this Journal*, 1964, 41, 295.

6. *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1962, 1020; Giri and Singh, *loc. cit.*

recrystallised from aqueous ethanol, m.p. 211°, yield 18 g.(71%). (Found: S, 12.12. C₁₀H₈ON₃ClS requires S, 12.62%). Other 2-chloroacetamido-substituted thiadiazoles, similarly prepared, are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

No.	Aryl.	M.P.	Yield.	Formula.	%Sulphur.	
					Found.	Reqd.
1	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	180°	66%	C ₁₀ H ₇ ON ₃ Cl ₂ S	10.98	11.11
2	<i>m</i> -Nitrophenyl	*216°	74	C ₁₀ H ₇ O ₂ N ₄ ClS	10.14	10.73
3	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	240°	67	C ₁₀ H ₇ O ₂ N ₄ ClS	10.02	10.73
4	<i>p</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	280°	70	C ₁₀ H ₈ O ₂ N ₃ ClS	11.62	11.87

*Melts with decomposition.

TABLE II

R.	M.P.	Yield.	Formula.	%Sulphur.	
				Found.	Reqd.
A. R' = R'' = Et.					
<i>m</i> -Nitro	209°	79%	C ₁₄ H ₁₇ O ₃ N ₃ S	9.41	9.55
<i>p</i> -Nitro	268°	74	C ₁₄ H ₁₇ O ₃ N ₃ S	9.45	9.55
<i>p</i> -Hydroxy	215.5°	65	C ₁₄ H ₁₈ O ₂ N ₃ S	10.64	10.46
<i>o</i> -Chloro	182°	78	C ₁₄ H ₁₇ ON ₃ ClS	9.74	9.86
B. R' = R'' = Ph.					
H	208°	66	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ ON ₃ S	8.26	8.29
<i>m</i> -Nitro	205°	70	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ O ₃ N ₃ S	7.39	7.42
<i>p</i> -Nitro	188°	78	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ O ₃ N ₃ S	7.28	7.42
<i>p</i> -Hydroxy	278-80°	64	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ O ₂ N ₃ S	7.84	7.96
<i>o</i> -Chloro	149-80°	71	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ ON ₃ ClS	7.89	7.00
C. R' = Et; R'' = Ph.					
H	175-76°	70	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ ON ₃ S	9.38	9.46
<i>m</i> -Nitro	128°	76	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ O ₃ N ₃ S	8.30	8.35
<i>p</i> -Nitro	242-44°	72	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ O ₃ N ₃ S	8.39	8.35
<i>p</i> -Hydroxy	270°	62	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ O ₂ N ₃ S	9.13	9.04
<i>o</i> -Chloro	199-98°	66	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ ON ₃ ClS	8.64	8.59
D.					
H	199-200°	61	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ ON ₃ S	10.53	10.69
<i>m</i> -Nitro	115°	67	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ O ₃ N ₃ S	9.28	9.22
<i>p</i> -Nitro	230°	70	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ O ₃ N ₃ S	9.18	9.22
<i>p</i> -Hydroxy	270°	76	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ O ₂ N ₃ S	10.12	10.06
<i>o</i> -Chloro	195°	68	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ ON ₃ ClS	9.38	9.51

Diethylamino-N-2-(5-phenyl-1,3,4-thiadiazol)ylacetamide.—To a solution of 2-chloroacetamido-5-phenyl-1,3,4-thiadiazole (12.5 g.) in ethanol (60 ml) was added an ethanolic solution of diethylamine (7.3 g.) and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 5 hr. Excess of the amine and of ethanol were removed and the residue was washed successively with sodium bicarbonate solution and water. It was recrystallised from benzene, m.p. 238°, yield 12.6 g. (88%). (Found: S, 10.84. $C_{14}H_{18}ON_4S$ requires S, 11.03%). Other basic acetamides, thus prepared, are recorded in Table II.

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